

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO THEIR JOB SATISFACTION

Javeed Ahmad Puju

*Assistant Professor, (Education), School of Open learning,
Directorate of Distance Education, University of Kashmir.*

&

Mastoora Hassan.

Contractual lecturer (Education), Govt. Degree College Boys Baramulla,

Abstract

The present study was carried out to find out the difference between rural and urban and male and female elementary school teachers on various dimension of job satisfaction. The investigators used Amar Singh and T.R Sharma's Job Satisfaction Scale(JSS). to collect the data randomly from various Govt. and private elementary schools. Some important statistical techniques were used to analyze and interpret the collected data and it was found that there is significant mean difference between rural and urban elementary school teachers further significant difference was found between male and female elementary school teachers.

Introduction

Education is responsible for healthy progress and development of any society. One of the basic purposes of education is to produce trained human resource, which can overcome development impediments of a given country. To achieve this, there should be a satisfied work force in the sector. Employees who have high level of job satisfaction commit their time, energy, and efforts to work which result in high productivity (Scott, 2004)

Elementary education is the foundation for the progress of the educational system in the country. To make elementary education strong and to empower whole nation

there is a rising need of well trained teachers who are satisfied and competent. Teachers are expected to fulfill all the basic requirements of the teaching learning situation, to make the learning situation pupil friendly and pronounce all possible efforts to make leaning possible in a healthy way.

Teachers are the main input source of any educational institution and teacher's adequate work and responsibility towards the institution makes it good or bad. Positive and favorable attitude make the work of a teacher not only easier but more satisfying and pleasant. On the other hand negative attitude makes the teaching work harder and unpleasant. The present teaching learning environment calls for teachers, who are able to approach the education of each child with a background of knowledge of the wide ranges in individual differences between them. So, it is the responsibility of teacher to impart quality education because they are in charge of the future of the nation.

For development of quality teachers one has to understand the factors associated with it. Job satisfaction is one of the important factor. Job satisfaction is defined as "the extent to which people like (satisfaction) or dislike (dissatisfaction) their jobs". One of the most widely used definitions of Locke (1976), defines job satisfaction as a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experiences. Thus, job satisfaction refers to the overall attitude and views of teachers towards their working conditions and profession.

Review Literature

The major purpose of reviewing the literature is to determine what has already been done that relates to the topic. It involves the systematic identification, location and analysis of documents containing information related to the research problem. The review tells what has been done and what wants to be done. A careful review of the research journals, books, dissertation, thesis and other sources of information on the problem to be investigated is one of the important steps in planning of any research study. Rashmi Sharma (2013) conducted research on "Teachers job satisfaction in

teaching profession”. The study reported that teachers level of job satisfaction has a positive relation with success in teaching. Annierah et al., (2013) examined Work performance and job satisfaction among teachers and found that the teachers display a high level of performance related skills, abilities, initiatives and productivity. Shashi Shukla (2014) conducted research on “Teaching competency Professional Commitment and Job Satisfaction—A study of primary school Teachers”. The study reported no relationship existing between teaching competency and job satisfaction. Singh and Pal (2011) carried out a study of job satisfaction and teaching effectiveness of school teachers. The study reported that there is a significantly higher correlation between job satisfaction and teaching effectiveness.

Need and Importance of the Study

This study has a multiple purpose. Primarily, the study will provide positive images of teachers towards teaching profession and develop insight in developing their potential role in society. This study is important because it assessed the present conditions of the teachers work performance and job satisfaction of teachers and professional growth of administrators towards better education. To prove the strength of our educational system we require teachers who are trained, and who are aware of their duties thus they will perform their jobs with the best they can afford. Job satisfaction affects various components of a job and is influenced by many other components as well. In the present study, efforts have been made to study the job satisfaction of elementary school teachers in private and government schools.

After analyzing the various studies carried out by different researchers, the investigator realized that no such research has been carried out on Elementary school teachers with reference to their Job satisfaction in Kashmir. Thus, the investigator found it burning issue to study teaching competency and Job Satisfaction of Elementary school teacher in District Ganderbal and District Srinagar.

Objectives

The investigators have formulated following objectives for the present study:

1. To study the job satisfaction of elementary school teachers.

2. To compare rural and urban elementary school teachers on various dimensions of job satisfaction.
3. To compare male and female elementary school teachers on various dimensions of job satisfaction.

Hypothesis

Following hypothesis have been formulated for the present investigation.

1. There is no significant mean difference between rural and urban elementary school teachers on job satisfaction.
2. There is no significant mean difference between male and female elementary school teachers on job satisfaction.

Methods and procedures

Sample:

The investigator shall select randomly 100 rural (50 male & 50 Female) and another 100 urban (50 male & 50 female) elementary school teachers from various elementary schools from district Ganderbal and district Srinagar.

Statistical techniques Used

The collected data shall be analyzed by applying some statistical techniques viz:

- Mean
- S.D
- T-value

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1.0: Shows mean comparisons of rural and urban elementary school teachers on dimension concrete factor of job satisfaction.

Category	N	Mea n	S.D	t- value	Level of significance
Rural	100	17.20	4.17	3.35	Significant
Urban	100	19.18	4.25		

The periodicals of above table shows comparison of rural and urban elementary school teacher on Concrete factor dimension of Job satisfaction. The table depicts that there is significant mean difference between rural and urban elementary school teachers at .01 levels. Urban elementary school teachers are more satisfied on dimension of concrete factor of job satisfaction as compared to rural elementary school teachers.

Table 1.1: Shows mean comparisons of rural and urban elementary school teachers on dimension job abstract factor of job satisfaction.

Category	N	Mean	S.D	t-value	Level of significance
Rural	100	18.15	4.10	1.84	insignificant
Urban	100	19.22	4.15		

The above table shows mean comparison of rural and urban elementary school teacher on Job Abstract dimension of Job satisfaction. The table depicts that there is no significant mean difference between rural and urban elementary school teachers at both levels. The table reveals that urban element school teachers scored higher mean than rural elementary school teachers but fails to reach any level of significant difference. Both rural and urban elementary school teachers shows same satisfaction on dimension of abstract factor of job satisfaction.

Table1.2: Shows mean comparisons of rural and urban elementary school teachers on dimensions psychological factor of job satisfaction.

Category	N	Mean	S.D	t-value	Level of significance
Rural	100	19.20	5.10	2.36	Significant at 0.05
Urban	100	20.90	5.18		

The data of above table shows comparison of rural and urban elementary school teacher on Psychological factor dimension of Job satisfaction. The table depicts that

there is significant difference between rural and urban elementary school teachers at 0.05 level. The table reveals that urban elementary school teachers are satisfied on dimension of psychological factor of job satisfaction.

Table1.3:Shows mean comparisons of rural and urban elementary school teachers on dimension economic factor of job satisfaction

Category	N	Mean	S.D	t-value	Level of significance
Rural	100	12.10	1.96	4.77	Significant
Urban	100	13.18	1.18		

The above table shows comparison of rural and urban elementary school teacher on economic factor dimension of Job satisfaction. The table depicts that there is significant mean difference between rural and urban elementary school teachers at both level of significance. Urban elementary school teachers are satisfied on dimension of concrete factor of job satisfaction

Table1.4: Shows mean comparisons of rural and urban elementary school teachers on dimension Community/National growth factor of job satisfaction

Category	N	Mean	S.D	t-value	Level of significance
Rural	100	11.76	2.39	2.08	Significant at 0.05
Urban	100	11.11	2.02		

The above table shows comparison of rural and urban elementary school teacher on Community/ National growth dimension of Job satisfaction. The table depicts that there is significant difference between rural and urban elementary school teachers at 0.05 levels. The table reveals that mean score favors rural elementary school teachers which depict they are more satisfied than urban elementary school teachers on dimension of community/national growth factor of job satisfaction.

Table1.5: Shows mean comparisons of male and female elementary school teachers on dimension job concrete factor of job satisfaction

Category	N	Mean	S.D	t-value	Level of significance
Male	100	16.20	3.17	4.4	Significant
Female	100	18.18	3.25		

The data of above table shows comparison of male and female elementary school teacher on Job concrete dimension of Job satisfaction. The table depicts that there is significant difference between male and female elementary school teachers at 0.05 and 0.01 levels. Female elementary school teachers are more satisfied on dimension of concrete factor of job satisfaction than their counter parts.

Table1.6:Shows mean comparisons of male and female elementary school teachers on dimension job abstract factor of job satisfaction

Category	N	Mean	S.D	t-value	Level of significance
Male	100	17.15	3.10	2.48	Significant at 0.05
Female	100	18.22	3.15		

The above table shows comparison of male and female elementary school teacher on Job abstract dimension of Job satisfaction. The table depicts that there is significant difference between male and female elementary school teachers at 0.05 but insignificant at 0.01 level. The table reveals that female elementary school teachers are satisfied on dimension of abstract factor of job satisfaction

Table1.7:Shows mean comparisons of male and female elementary school teachers on dimension psychological factor of job satisfaction

Category	N	Mean	S.D	t-value	Level of significance
Male	100	18.20	4.10	2.91	Significant
Female	100	19.90	4.18		

The above table shows comparison of male and female elementary school teacher on psychological dimension of Job satisfaction. The table depicts that there is significant difference between male and female elementary school teachers at 0.05 and 0.01 level. The table shows high mean score of female elementary school teachers which reflected they are satisfied on dimension of psychological factor of job satisfaction than their counter parts. .

Table1. 8: Shows mean comparisons of male and female elementary school teachers on dimension economic factor of job satisfaction

Category	N	Mean	S.D	t-value	Level of significance
Male	100	11.10	1.10	4.93	Significant
Female	100	12.18	1.90		

The data of above table shows comparison of male and female elementary school teacher on economic dimension of Job satisfaction. The table depicts that there is significant difference between male and female elementary school teachers at 0.05 and 0.01 levels. Female elementary school teachers are satisfied on dimension of economic factor of job satisfaction than male elementary school teachers. .

Table1.9:Shows mean comparisons of male and female elementary school teachers on dimension community/national growth factor of job satisfaction

Category	N	Mean	S.D	t-value	Level of significance
Male	100	10.76	1.39	3.88	Significant
Female	100	10.10	1.02		

The periodicals of above table shows comparison of male and female elementary school teacher on Community/ National growth dimension of Job satisfaction. The table depicts that there is significant difference between male and female elementary school teachers at both levels of significance. The tables shows female elementary school teachers are t satisfied on dimension of community /national growth factor of job satisfaction than their counter parts. .

Major findings.

1. It was found that there is significant mean difference between rural and urban elementary school teachers on concrete factor dimension of job satisfaction. Urban elementary teachers show more satisfaction on concrete factor of job satisfaction.
2. Further it was found that there is no significant mean difference between rural and urban elementary school teachers on job abstract dimensions of job satisfaction.
3. It was found that urban elementary school teachers show significant difference on psychological factor dimension of job satisfaction. Urban elementary school teacher are more satisfied on psychological factor of job satisfaction.
4. Significant mean difference was found between rural and urban elementary school teachers on economic factor dimension of job satisfaction. Urban elementary teachers show better satisfaction than rural elementary teachers.
5. It was also found that rural elementary school teachers shows better satisfaction than urban elementary school teachers on community/ national growth dimension of job satisfaction.
6. It was found that there is significant mean difference between rural and urban elementary school teachers on job satisfaction
7. It was further found that there is significant mean difference between male and female elementary school teachers on concrete factor dimension of job satisfaction. Female elementary teachers show better satisfaction on concrete fact as compared to their counter parts.
8. Female elementary school teachers were found somewhat satisfied than their counter parts while comparing on job abstract factor dimension of job satisfaction.
9. Significant men difference was found between male and female elementary school teachers while comparing on psychological factor dimension of job

satisfaction. Female teachers show more satisfaction than their counter parts.

10. It was also found that female elementary school teachers show significant mean difference on economic factor dimension of job satisfaction.
11. It was further found that there is significant mean difference between male and female elementary school teachers on community/ national growth dimension of job satisfaction. Male teachers show somewhat satisfaction than their counter parts.
12. It was also found that there is significant mean difference between male and female on job satisfaction.

References

- Annierah et.al (2013). "Work performance and Job satisfaction among teachers". International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Vol.3 no.5
- Cheng, Y., and Ren, L. (2010). Elementary Resource Room Teachers' Job Stress and Job Satisfaction. Journal of Intellectual and Development Disability, p.44.
- Deosthalee, P. G. (2002). Job Satisfaction of Teachers in comparison with non-teachers. Pakistan Journal of Psychological Research, p.81.
- Edwards, K. (2004). Perceptions of elementary school teachers. Dissertation Abstracts International,65(5),1023
- French, L., and Wagner, B. (2010). Motivation, Work Satisfaction, and Teacher Change Among Early Childhood Teachers. Journal of Research in Childhood Education, p. 152.
- French, L., and Wagner, B. (2010). Motivation, Work Satisfaction, and Teacher Change Among Early Childhood Teachers. Journal of Research in Childhood Education, p. 152.
- Klassen, R. M., Usher, E., Bong, M. (2010). Teachers' Collective Efficacy, Job Satisfaction, and Job Stress in Cross- Cultural Context. The Journal of Experimental Education, p. 464-486.

Rashmi, Sharma. (2013). Teachers job satisfaction in teaching profession. International Journal of Education and Psychological Research (JEPR) Vol 2, Issue3, pp.104.

Shashi Shukla (2014). Teaching competency, Professional commitment and Job satisfaction.- A study of Primary school teachers". Journal of research and method in education Vol 4, Issue 3, pp 44-64

Tillman, J, and Tillman, W. (2008). A Study of Job Satisfaction Among Teachers. Academy of Educational Leadership Journal, p. 1.